

SURVEILLANCE CARD_WNF_Pathogen detection in mosquitoes in non-endemic regions bordering endemic ones

	Characteristics	Description
1	Surveillance component name	Pathogen detection in mosquitoes in non-endemic regions bordering endemic ones.
2	Surveillance aim	Early detection of a change of the geographic distribution/spread of the virus to new areas; Early detection of the introduction of the pathogen; mosquito identification; mosquito abundancy.
3	Target species and group	<i>Culex pipiens</i> ; <i>Culex modestus</i> ; <i>Culex perexiguus</i> ; <i>Culex torrentium</i> ; <i>Culex univittatus</i>
4	Target sector / production type	Not applicable.
5	Geographical area covered	Country-wide areas with suitable habitat for mosquitoes; <i>Culex pipiens</i> is found in all European countries, except Iceland and Faroe Islands, and in all Middle Eastern and North African countries. (1)
6	Age group	Adult mosquitoes. (2)
7	Sampling point and strategy	Areas with suitable habitat for vectors: to be preferred areas where adult female mosquitoes lay eggs on the surface of fresh or stagnant water. Areas on the outskirts of cities and population centres, bordering forests and wetlands. [2] to be conducted with host-seeking/gravid traps.
8	Sampling time period	Minimum annual time frame with the greatest diffusion of vectors: from March to November. (2)
9	Sampling matrix	The whole mosquito.
10	Type of disease indicators	Virus identification and isolation; Minimal Infection Rate (MIR).
11	Sampling unit	Mosquito pools; pooling unfed females by location/time, max pool of 10 – 50. [VectorNet, 2022]

12	Allocation of animal groups /animals to sampling	All trapped unfed female vector species.
13	Testing protocol / Diagnostic test	PCR on pooled unfed adult females. (2)
14	Design prevalence (only relevant for probability-based sampling)	Not applicable; biased (non-random or non-representative) sample of the population
15	Level of confidence (only relevant for probability-based sampling)	Not applicable; biased (non-random or non-representative) sample of the population
16	Contribution of the component to the surveillance system	Complementary to sentinel birds, wild bird, human, horse surveillance. Low compared to sentinel birds, wild bird, human, horse surveillance.
17	Other pathogens that could be targeted with this surveillance component	RVF, Usutu Viruses, canine dirofilarial worms, and avian malaria parasites in Europe. (1)
18	References	1) ECDC Culex pipiens - Factsheet for experts, last updated 15 Jun 2020 2) CDC Culex Species Mosquito Life Cycle Factsheet, 2022 3) EFSA External scientific report Risk of vector-borne diseases for the EU: Entomological aspects: Part 2; Marieta Braks, Giuseppe Mancini, Marieke de Swart, Maria Goffredo First published: 10 March 2017
19	Additional comments	Prevalence information available: 0.005-25% Minimum infection rate (MIR) (3)